

Kinetics and Mechanism of Thallium(III)–Ligand Electron Transfer Reactions. Oxidation of 2-Furoic Acid in Perchloric Acid Solutions

K. S. GUPTA*, DINESH KUMAR**, (Mrs.) RACHNA BHARGAVA, (Miss) ASHU RANI and D. S. N. PRASAD

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

In the oxidation of 2-furoic acid (HFA) with thallic perchlorate at 55°, several Tl^{III} –HFA complexes are formed and the complex $Tl(HFA)_2^+$ appears to be only reactive species. When at constant $[Tl^{III}]_T$, the HFA is increased the rate profile passes through a maximum. At very high $[HFA]_T/[Tl^{III}]_T$ ratio, the following rate law is obeyed,

$$-\frac{d[Tl^{III}]}{dt} = \frac{k[Tl^{III}]_T}{1 + K_4[HFA]_T}$$

where K_4 is the formation constant of $Tl(HFA)_2^+$ from $Tl(HFA)_2^+$ and k is the rate constant for the decomposition of latter into products.

The thallium(III)-ligand electron transfer reactions have also been reviewed and it appears that inner-sphere mechanism is preponderant.

DURING the last three decades a large number of thallium(III)-ligand electron transfer reactions have been studied and the accumulation of sufficient kinetic data warrants their analysis and correlation. The early investigations were aimed at eliciting whether the reduction of Tl^{III} occurred in two steps of 1-equivalent change via Tl^{II} or in a single step of 2-electron transfer¹. For later investigators, the resolution of the issue of intermediate complex formation and nature of the electron transfer mode – outer-sphere or inner-sphere became more important². In between, some work on correlation of reaction rates of organic substrates in terms of linear free energy relationships³ (LFERs) has also been reported. The reactions of organic compounds were reviewed⁴ in 1973, and those of non-metallic inorganic compounds are yet to be reviewed.

The present paper consists of two parts. In the first part, the kinetics of the oxidation of 2-furoic acid is reported and in the second part, the mechanistic features of thallium(III)-ligand reactions have been reviewed.

The interest in studying the oxidation of 2-furancarboxylic acid (2-furoic acid, henceforth referred to as HFA) arose from a variety of reasons. Firstly, the oxidation of any furan compound with thallium(III) has not been studied. Secondly, very few oxidation studies of HFA have been made. Finally, it was of interest to know whether the electron transfer was accomplished via an inner-sphere or an outer-sphere mechanism.

Experimental

Kinetic procedure: 2-Furoic acid (Koch-Light, pure) was used as such. As its solution was found

to deteriorate on standing, it was always prepared fresh. All other chemicals and the procedure for following the kinetics by iodometric method were the same as described earlier¹. The interference in the iodometric estimation of Tl^{III} due to a slow reaction between iodine and HFA was checked by performing the titration in the ice-cold conditions. The kinetics were studied at $55 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and the results were reproducible within $\pm 5\%$.

Stoichiometry: The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by allowing a known amount of thallic perchlorate to react with a known amount of HFA which was always in deficit at 55° for more than 3 days to ensure completion of the reaction. The unreacted Tl^{III} was estimated iodometrically. The results indicate that one mole of HFA requires one mole of Tl^{III} .

Products: The oxidation of HFA gave different products with different oxidants, e.g. malealdehydic acid⁵ with PbO_2 , and maleic, fumaric and succinic acids with Caro's acid⁶. In our case, the intermediate product malealdehyde was identified by Milas's test⁷. The final product succinaldehydic acid was isolated and identified as follows. The reaction mixture was extracted by solvent ether thrice. The ethereal layer was washed with distilled water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and concentrated under reduced pressure over a steam-bath. The concentrated mass was found to be a viscous oil whose identity as succinaldehydic acid was supported by ir spectrum.

In our case, the expected product consistent with 2-electron change and the decarboxylation is malealdehyde. In our experimental conditions, malealdehyde is not stable and is reported to arrange to

*Department of Chemistry, M. S. College, Saharanpur, U.P

give succinaldehydic acid⁸. The net reaction can be written as

Spectrophotometric study of complexation equilibria: In order to study Ti^{III} –HFA complexation equilibria, optical density measurements were made on a Pye- Unicam Spectrophotometer with 1 cm cells at 25°. At 300 nm, neither Ti^{III} nor HFA had any absorbance but their mixtures absorbed strongly at the same wave length. Absorbances of the mixtures of Ti^{III} with different concentrations of HFA were noted (Fig. 1). A plot of the $[\text{absorbance}]^{-1}$ vs $[\text{HFA}]_T^{-1}$ yielded a straight line with an intercept, and from this the apparent stability constant of the ultimate complex was determined to be 60 ± 2 at 25° and $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.5 \text{ M}$.

Fig. 1. Absorbance of mixtures of Ti^{III} and furoic acid at 300 nm; $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.5 \text{ M}$, temp. = 25°; $[\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}] = (\text{O}) 1 \times 10^{-3}$, $(\Delta) 2 \times 10^{-3}$ and $(\bullet) 3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$.

Results and Discussion

2-Furoic acid dependence: The results of the variation of HFA are complicated but interesting. The $[\text{HFA}]$ was varied in the range $1.0 - 9.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ at $[\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}]_T = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.5 \text{ M}$, $I = 1.0 \text{ M}$ (maintained with LiClO_4) and $t = 55^\circ$. When HFA is low there is almost no reaction and this situation persists till $[\text{HFA}]/[\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}]$ ratio becomes ~ 2 . Thereafter, with the increase in $[\text{HFA}]$, the rate starts increasing, reaches a maximum and with further

increase in $[\text{HFA}]_T$ the rate starts declining and continues to do so. The results are given in Table 1 and Fig. 2. A similar situation arises when $[\text{HFA}]$ is varied at two more $[\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}]_T = 3 \times 10^{-3}$ and $4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$. The rate maxima occur at $[\text{HFA}]_T/[\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}]_T$ ratios of ~ 12 , ~ 10 and ~ 9 at $[\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}]$ of 2.0×10^{-3} , 3×10^{-3} and $4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ respectively.

Fig. 2. Plot of initial rate vs [2-furoic acid]; $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.5 \text{ M}$, $I = 1.0 \text{ M}$, temp. = 55°; $[\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}] = (\text{O}) 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$, $(\bullet) 3.0 \times 10^{-3}$ and $(\Delta) 4.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF INITIAL RATES FOR OXIDATION OF 2-FUROIC ACID BY Ti^{III} AT 55°

$[\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}]$ $\times 10^3 \text{ M}$	$[\text{HFA}]$ $\times 10^3 \text{ M}$	$[\text{HClO}_4]$ M	I M	R_{obs} $\times 10^7 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$	R_{cal} $\times 10^7 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$
2.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	—	—
2.0	2.0	0.5	1.0	—	—
2.0	3.0	0.5	1.0	—	—
2.0	4.0	0.5	1.0	—	—
2.0	6.0	0.5	1.0	1.8	—
2.0	8.0	0.5	1.0	15.2	—
2.0	10.0	0.5	1.0	18.5	—
2.0	12.0	0.5	1.0	24.2	—
2.0	16.0	0.5	1.0	27.5	—
2.0	20.0	0.5	1.0	36.0	—
2.0	24.0	0.5	1.0	43.3	—
2.0	32.0	0.5	1.0	33.8	81.2
2.0	40.0	0.5	1.0	27.7	26.8
2.0	48.0	0.5	1.0	24.4	23.5
2.0	56.0	0.5	1.0	21.8	20.9
2.0	60.0	0.5	1.0	20.0	19.8
2.0	70.0	0.5	1.0	18.0	17.5
2.0	80.0	0.5	1.0	15.8	15.7
2.0	90.0	0.5	1.0	13.1	14.2
3.0	10.0	0.5	1.0	23.3	—
3.0	16.0	0.5	1.0	31.6	—
3.0	20.0	0.5	1.0	39.0	—
3.0	24.0	0.5	1.0	49.0	—
3.0	30.0	0.5	1.0	56.0	61.6
3.0	32.0	0.5	1.0	53.7	58.6
3.0	36.0	0.5	1.0	51.7	54.5
3.0	40.0	0.5	1.0	50.2	50.7

(Table 1 contd.)

9.0	50.0	0.5	1.0	49.2	49.2
9.0	60.0	0.5	1.0	37.9	37.7
3.0	70.0	0.5	1.0	35.0	38.3
9.0	80.0	0.5	1.0	30.9	30.3
3.0	90.0	0.5	1.0	28.9	27.2
9.0	100.0	0.5	1.0	28.6	24.8
3.0	110.0	0.5	1.0	21.7	22.9
3.0	120.0	0.5	1.0	20.1	21.2
4.0	8.0	0.5	1.0	19.4	
4.0	12.0	0.5	1.0	28.7	
4.0	20.0	0.5	1.0	49.3	
4.0	30.0	0.5	1.0	61.7	
4.0	36.0	0.5	1.0	70.0	
4.0	40.0	0.5	1.0	60.0	67.6
4.0	50.0	0.5	1.0	55.0	57.6
4.0	60.0	0.5	1.0	51.7	50.2
4.0	70.0	0.5	1.0	46.7	44.4
4.0	80.0	0.5	1.0	49.3	39.9
4.0	90.0	0.5	1.0	38.9	36.2
4.0	100.0	0.5	1.0	36.0	33.1
4.0	110.0	0.5	1.0	31.6	30.5
4.0	120.0	0.5	1.0	29.2	28.9
1.0	100.0	1.0	1.0	7.6	8.8
1.5	100.0	1.0	1.0	11.0	12.4
2.0	100.0	1.0	1.0	15.3	16.5
3.0	100.0	1.0	1.0	23.3	24.8
4.0	100.0	1.0	1.0	31.0	33.1
5.0	100.0	1.0	1.0	38.0	41.3
6.0	100.0	1.0	1.0	48.0	49.6
2.0	10.0	0.5	1.5	15.2	
2.0	10.0	0.8	1.5	15.2	
2.0	10.0	1.2	1.5	15.2	
2.0	10.0	1.5	1.5	15.8	
2.0	24.0	0.5	1.5	36.0	
2.0	24.0	0.7	1.5	36.0	
2.0	24.0	0.9	1.5	36.0	
2.0	24.0	1.1	1.5	37.2	
2.0	24.0	1.3	1.5	36.0	
2.0	24.0	1.5	1.5	36.0	
2.0	50.0	0.5	1.5	20.0	
2.0	50.0	0.8	1.5	20.0	
2.0	50.0	1.2	1.5	20.0	
2.0	50.0	1.5	1.5	20.0	
2.0	30.0	0.5	0.5	34.4	
2.0	30.0	0.5	1.0	32.0	
2.0	30.0	0.5	1.5	29.2	
2.0	30.0	0.5	2.0	26.8	

Thallium(III) dependence : The results of [HFA] variation indicate that several relatively strong complexes between Tl^{III} and HFA are formed and their relative population depends on $[HFA]/[Tl^{III}]$ ratio. However, at high HFA, only penultimate and ultimate thallium(III)–HFA complexes would be present so the concentration of Tl^{III} was varied between 1.0×10^{-3} and $6.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ in order to determine the reaction order in Tl^{III} . In all these experiments, $[HFA]_T/[Tl^{III}]_T$ ratio was $\sim 14-100$. The plot of initial rate vs $[Tl^{III}]_i$ was a straight line passing through origin, indicating the order in Tl^{III} to be one. In pseudo-first order conditions, [HFA] was at least ten times in excess over $[Tl^{III}]$; pseudo-first order plots were not good straight lines. This is obviously due to the fact that during a single run, as the reaction progresses, the $[Tl^{III}]$ decreases resulting in the change of $[HFA]_T/[Tl^{III}]_T$ ratio which influences the relative population of different thallium(III)–furoic acid complexes which have different reactivity. However, in some experiment, $[HFA]_T/[Tl^{III}]_T$ ratio was more than 60 times, the

pseudo-first order plots between $\log [Tl^{III}]_i$ and time were good straight lines and the values of k_{obs} were independent of $[Tl^{III}]_i$ which further confirms that the order in Tl^{III} is one. In view of the complex nature of the reaction, the entire treatment of the kinetic results is based on the initial rates which are given in Table 1.

Hydrogen ion and ionic strength dependence : The influence of $[H^+]$ on the reaction rate was investigated by varying the $[HClO_4]$ in the range 0.5–1.5 *M* keeping ionic strength fixed at 1.5 *M* with $LiClO_4$. The results of $HClO_4$ variation (0.5–1.5 *M*) at $I=1.5 M$ indicate that there is no significant effect of $[H^+]$ on the reaction rate (Table 1). It may be mentioned that in the oxidation of H_3PO_3 , $HCOOH^o$ and amides¹⁰⁻¹² too, the hydrogen ions did not affect the reaction rate. The increase in ionic strength from 0.5 to 2 *M* with $LiClO_4$ decreased the rate by about 20% only (Table 1).

Rate law and mechanism : The dissociation constant¹³ of HFA is 7.1×10^{-4} and so in the range 0.5–1.0 *M* $HClO_4$ used in most of the experiments, it would be present almost completely as undissociated molecule. Under similar acidity conditions, Tl^{III} would be present as Tl^{3+} or its complexes with HFA. Its hydrolysed form would be negligible due to its low hydrolysis constant¹⁴, 7.3×10^{-8} at 25° and $I=3.0 M$.

The results (Table 1, Fig. 2) clearly indicate that several Tl^{III} –HFA complexes are formed and these complexes react differently. Thus, the most important point in constructing the reaction mechanism is the number of complexes formed between Tl^{III} and HFA. The literature is silent on this point. The spectrophotometry too could give the stability constant of the ultimate complex only and the value is 60 ± 2 at 25°. The stability constants of lower complexes are therefore expected to be much larger than this value as per statistical requirements¹⁵. This is further supported by the observance of the rate maxima at nearly the same $[HFA]_T/[Tl^{III}]_T$ ratios of ~ 12 , ~ 10 and ~ 9 at different concentrations of Tl^{III} (Fig. 2). From a study of the complex formation between Tl^{III} and several carboxylic acids¹⁶, such as acetic, salicylic and some dicarboxylic acids, it is easy to infer that generally no more than tetracoordinated complexes are formed. Analogously, it is assumed that in the present system too, only four complexes, namely, $[Tl(HFA)_1]^{3+}$, $[Tl(HFA)_2]^{3+}$ and $[Tl(HFA)_3]^{3+}$ and $[Tl(HFA)_4]^{3+}$ are formed. This is corroborated to some extent by the nature of the curves in Fig. 2. The kinetic results require the presence of at least three complexes in the region of maximum rate, and further, the middle complex should either be more reactive than the other two complexes or be the only reactive complex in order to explain the occurrence of maximum in the rate profile.

There is virtually no reaction at $[HFA]_T/[Tl^{III}]_T$ ratio ~ 2 (Table 1) and the species which are most

likely to be present in this region are Tl^{3+} , $[Ti(HFA)]^{3+}$ and $[Ti(HFA)_2]^{3+}$. The stability constants K_1 and K_2 of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes are expected to have high value as argued earlier¹⁵. The most likely conclusion that can be drawn is that $[Ti(HFA)]^{3+}$ and $[Ti(HFA)_2]^{3+}$ are unreactive, and further, there is no direct reaction between Tl_{aq}^{3+} and HFA too. As $[HFA]$ is increased, the concentration of $[Ti(HFA)_2]^{3+}$ starts building up. It appears that this complex is reactive and as a consequence the rate also starts increasing (Fig. 2). At the rate maximum, the relative population of this species appears to attain a maximal value. Further increase in HFA results in the formation of more of unreactive $[Ti(HFA)_4]^{3+}$. Thus, beyond rate maximum with increase in $[HFA]$, reactive $[Ti(HFA)_2]^{3+}$ is being converted progressively into unreactive $[Ti(HFA)_4]^{3+}$, and hence in line with this, the rate of the reaction also continues to decrease. It is interesting to point out that almost similar kinetic results were obtained in the oxidation of HNO_2 ¹⁷. The formation of three thallium(III)-nitrite complexes was assumed and the complex $[Ti(NO_2)_2]^{+}$ was considered to be reactive.

On the basis of the arguments presented so far, it is now possible to propose the following mechanism.

where K_1 , K_2 , K_3 and K_4 are the step-wise formation constants of the respective complexes and k is the rate constant for the decomposition of $[Ti(HFA)_2]^{3+}$. Assuming that around rate maxima only $[Ti(HFA)_2]^{3+}$, $[Ti(HFA)_3]^{3+}$ and $[Ti(HFA)_4]^{3+}$ are present, the rate law (7) may be derived. In rate law (7), $[Ti^{III}]_i$ is initial concentration of Ti^{III} .

$$\frac{-d[Ti^{III}]}{dt} = \frac{kK_1K_2K_3[Ti^{III}]_i[HFA]^2}{K_1K_2[HFA]^2 + K_1K_2K_3[HFA]^3 + K_1K_2K_3K_4[HFA]^4} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{-d[Ti^{III}]}{dt} = \frac{kK_2[Ti^{III}]_i[HFA]}{1 + K_2[HFA] + K_2K_4[HFA]^2} \quad (8)$$

$[HFA]$ is free or uncomplexed ligand, while $[HFA]_T$ is its analytical concentration. In the region beyond maximum where HFA is quite high, it is reasonable to surmise that only two complexes $[Ti(HFA)_2]^{3+}$

and $[Ti(HFA)_4]^{3+}$ are present and the rate law (8) reduces to

$$R_{obs} = \frac{-d[Ti^{III}]}{dt} = \frac{k[Ti^{III}]_i}{1 + K_4[HFA]_T} \quad (9)$$

In rate law (9), $[HFA]$ has been replaced by $[HFA]_T$ as 2-furoic acid is in larger concentration than $[Ti^{III}]_i$, and R_{obs} is the initial rate. In conformity with the rate law (9), the plots of $1/R_{obs}$ vs $[HFA]_T$ were good straight lines yielding K_4 and k values of 60, 58, 56 l and 4.55×10^{-8} , 5.55×10^{-8} , 5.55×10^{-8} (av. $5.2 \pm 0.5 \times 10^{-8}$) $dm^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively at $[Ti^{III}]_i = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$, 3.0×10^{-3} , $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $I = 1.0 M$, and $t = 55^\circ$. In view of the complicated nature of the reaction, the agreement among k and K_4 values determined at different $[Ti^{III}]_i$ is considered excellent. The K_4 value of 60 ± 2 as determined spectrophotometrically is also in excellent agreement. This reinforces the validity of the rate treatment and the proposed mechanism. The values of R_{obs} as determined experimentally are in good agreement with the R_{cal} values as calculated from the rate law (9). Since the values of K_1 , K_2 and K_3 are neither available nor could be determined spectrophotometrically, quantitative analysis of the kinetic results prior to rate maximum could not be carried out.

It is worth noting that undissociated 2-furoic acid molecule rather than its anion appears to take part in the complexation. There are many examples of this type in the literature. Formic acid molecule is reported to complex Mn_{aq}^{2+} ¹⁸, Co_{aq}^{2+} ¹⁹ and Ce_{aq}^{4+} ²⁰, prior to its oxidation. Similarly, Tl_{aq}^{3+} too forms reactive complexes with undissociated molecules of formic⁹ and hypophosphorous¹ acids.

The situation of one complex being reactive and the others unreactive is not unique to this reaction alone. Higher complexes of oxalate in thallium(III)-oxalic acid²¹ and of thiocyanate in thallium(III)-thiocyanate²² reactions are also not reactive. A similar situation prevails in Ti^{III} - HNO_2 reaction¹⁷ also. In the Ti^{III} - Ti^I exchange reaction $TiCl_2^+$ is less reactive than higher chlorothallium(III) complexes²³, $Ti(CN)^{2+}$ and $Ti(CN)_2^+$ are inert but higher complexes are reactive²⁴. On the other hand, in U^{III} - Ti^{III} reaction²⁵, 1:1 complex of Ti^{III} and fumaric acid is more reactive than the higher complexes.

There are several important questions about the mechanistic features of Ti^{III} -L electron transfer reactions. First we consider the question of rate law and stoichiometric mechanism. Based on kinetic evidence for the formation of one or more Ti^{III} -L complexes or absence of it and the nature of hydrogen ion dependence, the Ti^{III} -L reactions may be grouped into five categories.

Category 1: In the reactions of this type there is kinetic evidence for the formation of Ti^{III} -L complex but the rate of the reaction is independent

of H^+ in conformity with the rate law (10) and general reaction mechanism (11),

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{kK[Tl^{III}]_T[L]}{1+K[L]} \quad (10)$$

with $[Tl^{III}]_T$ in deficit.

The oxidations of $H_2PO_3^1$, $HCOOH^9$, $HCONH_2^{10}$ and oximes²⁶ of benzaldehyde and acetophenone are of this type. The values of k and K are collected in Table 2. A minor variation of the rate law occurs in the oxidation of substituted hydrazines where the protonation of the ligand takes place but the unprotonated form is reactive.

TABLE 2—RATE AND EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS k AND K FOR Tl^{III} -LIGAND ELECTRON TRANSFER REACTIONS

Reductant	Intermediate complex	t °C	K	$k \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
H_2PO_3	$[Tl(H_2PO_3)]^{2+}$	25 ^a	12.8	8
$HCOOH$	$[TlHCOOH]^{2+}$	74 ^b	16	1.7
		70 ^c	14	0.7
$HCONH_2$	$[TlHCONH_2]^{2+}$	70 ^d	0.6	7.2
Oxime of benzaldehyde	$[Tl\text{-oxime}]^{2+}$	45 ^e	520	3.2×10^3
Oxime of acetophenone	$[Tl\text{-oxime}]^{2+}$	45 ^e	2×10^3	63
H_2PO_2	$[Tl(H_2PO_2)]^{2+}$	60 ^f	30	0.88
HRSH	$[TlSRH]^{2+}$	25 ^g	1650	3.78
H_2O_2	$[Tl(O_2)]^{2+}$	25 ^h	855	0.31
HNO_2	$[Tl(NO_2)]^{2+}$	25 ⁱ	653	39
Glycolic HGA	$[Tl(GA)]^{2+}$	70 ^j	1.1	0.69
Glyoxylic (HGOX)	$[Tl(GOX)]^{2+}$	70 ^j	625	1.1
Hydroxyisobutyric acid (HIBA)	$[Tl(IBA)]^{2+}$	70 ^k	1.2	1.0
HFA	$[Tl(HFA)]^{2+}$	55	58 ^l	5.2

^aRef. 1, ^bRef. 9, ^cRef. 9, ^dRef. 10, ^eRef. 26, ^fRef. 28, ^gRef. 29, ^hRef. 21, ⁱRef. 17, ^jRef. 31, ^kRef. 32, ^lPresent work.

Category 2: The reactions of this category differ from the first in being hydrogen ion dependent consistent with rate law (12).

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{kK[Tl^{III}][HL]}{H^+ + K[HL]} \quad (12)$$

The intermediate complex may be formed by any or all of the following equilibria :

It can be shown²⁸ that the rate law derived from the mechanism (13–17) would reduce to experimental rate law (12). The oxidation of $H_2PO_3^{26}$, thiomalic acid²⁹ and oxalic acid³¹ (where instead of one, two protons are released during complexation) are of this type. The k and K values are given in Table 2.

Category 3: In the reactions of this type more than one kinetically detectable thallium(III)-ligand complexes are formed. All or one or more of these complexes may be reactive. The complexation may or may not be accompanied by deprotonation. If in the successive complexes, the reactivity increases with increase in coordination number, the rate will continuously increase with increase in $[Ligand]$. On the other hand, an opposite effect will be observed, if with the increase in $[Ligand]$, successively less reactive complexes are formed. Examples of this type have not come to our notice.

If one of the middle complexes, for example, 1:2 or 1:3 happens to be more reactive than the others or be only reactive, the rate profile will have a maximum as in Fig. 1. The reactions of nitrous acid¹⁷, glycolic³¹, glyoxylic³¹ and α -hydroxyisobutyric acids³² exhibit this kind of behaviour. The present oxidation of HFA is also of the same type and the rate law observed is of the type (8) consistent with mechanism (2–6) or a variation of it. In case, one of the middle complexes happens to be less reactive than the rest, the rate profile will pass through a minimum. No example of this kind of behaviour has come to our notice. Values of k and K for some reactions are given in Table 2.

Category 4: In the reactions of this kind there is no kinetic evidence for thallium(III)-ligand complex formation but the rate of reaction decreases with increasing $[H^+]$. In this case, the complex formation has been assumed but its stability constant is so low that the complex can not be detected kinetically. The common rate law obeyed by the reaction of this type is as follows :

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 \frac{[Tl^{III}][L]}{[H^+]} \quad (18)$$

or a minor variation of it. The reaction mechanism is of the same type as in category 2. The oxidations of As^{III} ³³, hydrazine^{34–37} and its derivatives³⁰, hydroxylamine³⁸, 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl³⁹, 1,2-dihydroxy aromatic derivatives⁴⁰, 1-hydroxy-2-methoxybenzene⁴¹, quinol⁴², L-rhamnose⁴³, aldose³, phenol⁴⁴, tartronic and mesoxalic acids⁴⁵, 1,4-dihydroxybenzene⁴⁶ are of this type. The values of composite rate constant k_2 which is equal to kK (13–17) are given in Table 3.

Category 5: The reactions of this category have a clearcut first order dependence in each of Tl^{III} and ligand without any $[H^+]$ dependence. A minor term in $[H^+]$ dependence may be associated with the ligand whose undissociated form is reactive. The rate law obeyed is

$$\text{Rate} = k_3 [Tl^{III}][L] \quad (19)$$

TABLE 3—VALUES OF COMPOSITE RATE CONSTANT k_2^* FOR TlIII-LIGAND ELECTRON TRANSFER REACTIONS

Reductant	Intermediate complex	t °C	k_2 $\times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3$ $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
H_2AsO_2^a	$[\text{TlH}_2\text{AsO}_2]^{2+}$	35	1.475×10^4
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{OH}^b$	$[\text{TlOC}_6\text{H}_5]^{2+}$	25	8.3×10^7
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{OH}^b$	$[\text{Cl}_2\text{TlOC}_6\text{H}_5]^{2+}$	25	1.2×10^6
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{OH}^b$	$[\text{Cl}_2\text{TlOC}_6\text{H}_5]^{2+}$	25	1.0×10^4
Hydrazine ^c	$[\text{TlN}_2\text{H}_4]^{2+}$	8	8.4×10^4
Hydrazine ^d	$[(\text{OAc})_2\text{TlN}_2\text{H}_4]^{2+}$	8	4.0×10^3
Hydrazine ^d	$[(\text{OAc})_2\text{TlN}_2\text{H}_4]^{2+}$	8	9.6×10^3
Hydroxylamine ^e	$[\text{TlN}_2\text{HOH}]^{2+}$	8	60
4,4'-Dihydroxy-diphenyl (L) ^f	$[(\text{HOTl})]^{2+}$	25	1.54×10^6
1,4-Dihydroxybenzene (L) ^g	$[(\text{HOTl})]^{2+}$	25	2.5×10^7
$\text{ICH}_2\text{CONH}_2(\text{L})^h$	$[(\text{HOTl})]^{2+}$	25	2.1×10^7
$\text{ClCH}_2\text{CONH}_2(\text{L})^h$	$[(\text{HOTl})]^{2+}$	40	6.0
Quinol (H_2q) ⁱ	$[(\text{HOTl H}_2\text{q})]^{2+}$	40	19
1-Hydroxy-4-methoxybenzene (Hhmb) ^j	$[(\text{HOTl Hhmb})]^{2+}$	25	2.1×10^7
1,4-Dihydroxy-2-methylbenzene (H_2dhmb) ^h	$[(\text{HOTl H}_2\text{dhmb})]^{2+}$	25	1.6×10^7
Catechol (L) ⁱ	$[(\text{HOTl})]^{2+}$	25	4.0×10^9
Guaiacol (L) ⁱ	$[(\text{HOTl})]^{2+}$	25	14×10^9
Phenylhydrazine (L) ^j	$[(\text{Cl}_2\text{TlL})]$	25	4×10^7
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl hydrazine (L) ^j	$[(\text{Cl}_2\text{TlL})]$	25	470
2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazine (L) ^j	$[(\text{Cl}_2\text{TlL})]$	25	350
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl hydrazine (L) ^j	$[(\text{Cl}_2\text{TlL})]$	25	2500
<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl hydrazine (L) ^k	$[(\text{Cl}_2\text{TlL})]$	30	1380
	$[(\text{Cl}_2\text{TlL})]$	30	2100

* k_2 may include equilibrium constant for TlIII-L complexation equilibrium.

^aRef. 33, ^bRef. 41, ^cRef. 36, ^dRef. 37, ^eRef. 38, ^fRef. 39, ^gRef. 62, ^hRef. 56, ⁱRef. 40, ^jRef. 30, ^kRef. 27.

and the mechanism generally proposed is

Obviously K has a very low value. However, there is no way to distinguish this mechanism from the following single-step bimolecular path.

According to rate law (19) and mechanism (20), $k_2 = kK$. The oxidation of *N*-methylformamide^{1,2}, *N,N*-dimethylformamide by Ti^{3+} and the reduction of chlorothallium(III) complexes by $\text{H}_2\text{PO}_3^{4,6}$, $\text{H}_2\text{PO}_3^{4,7}$ exhibit this kind of kinetics. The rate constant k_2 for several reactions are given in Table 4.

It is pertinent to state here that the categories (1-5) do cover most of the cases but certainly not all. For example, an exceptional order of two has been found^{3,4,8} in Ti^{III} in $\text{Ti}^{III}-\text{SCN}^-$ reaction although stoichiometrically Ti^{III} and SCN^- react in the ratio of 1 and 3. Also in the oxidation of H_2O_2 by Ti^{III} the order in H_2O_2 is two while they react in 1 : 1 ratio.

TABLE 4—VALUES OF COMPOSITE RATE CONSTANTS k_2^*

Oxidant	Reductant	t °C	k_2 $\times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3$ $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
TiCl_2^{2+} ^a	H_2PO_3	55	2.52
TiCl_2^{2+} ^a	H_2PO_3	55	8.2
TiCl_2^{2+} ^a	H_2PO_3	55	27
TiCl_2^{2+} ^a	H_2PO_3	55	81
TiCl_2^{2+} ^b	H_2PO_3	28	67
TiCl_2^{2+} ^b	H_2PO_3	28	280
TiCl_2^{2+} ^b	H_2PO_3	28	1250
TiCl_2^{2+} ^b	H_2PO_3	28	2400
Ti^{3+} ^c	<i>N</i> -Methylformamide	70	0.8
Ti^{3+} ^d	Dimethylformamide	70	0.55
Ti^{3+} ^e	1,4-Dihydroxybenzene	25	6.8×10^6
Ti^{3+} ^e	4,4'-Dihydroxy-diphenyl	25	3.0×10^6
Ti^{3+} ^f	Quinol	25	6.8×10^3
Ti^{3+} ^g	1-Hydroxy-4-methoxybenzene	25	3.1×10^3
Ti^{3+} ^g	1,4-Dihydroxy-2-methylbenzene	25	16×10^3
Ti^{3+} ^h	$\text{ClCH}_2\text{CONH}_2$	40	8.5
Ti^{3+} ^h	$\text{ICH}_2\text{CONH}_2$	40	3.5
Ti^{3+} ⁱ	Propan-2-ol	45	7.05×10^{-3}
Ti^{3+} ⁱ	Pentan-2-ol	45	20.3×10^{-3}
Ti^{3+} ⁱ	1,3-Dichloropropan-2-ol	50	7.0×10^{-3}

* k_2 may include equilibrium constant for $\text{Ti}^{III}-\text{L}$ complexation equilibrium.

^aRef. 47, ^bRef. 46, ^cRef. 12, ^dRef. 11, ^eRef. 39, ^fRef. 43, ^gRef. 38, ^hRef. 62, ⁱRef. 60.

Now we turn our attention to the issue of molecular mechanism, i.e. the electron transfer in $\text{Ti}^{III}-\text{L}$ reaction occurs through outer-sphere or inner-sphere paths. First, we consider the outer-sphere case. The ligand substitution rate^{3,4,9} for Ti^{3+} is $> 10^8 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, and till to-date no redox reaction of Ti^{III} is known to have such a high rate. Obviously no redox reaction of Ti^{III} can be classed as outer-sphere outright, although the possibility of this mechanism operating in slower reactions does exist. In case of a large number of $\text{Ti}^{III}-\text{L}$ electron transfer reactions, the ambiguity about the two paths persists, although most of the workers prefer an inner-sphere mechanism. Some of the arguments advanced in support of this hypothesis run as follows.

It is generally found that addition of complexing ligands which themselves do not suffer any oxidation or reduction in general cut the rate of the reaction drastically^{3,4,8,44,50-52}. The oxidation of hydrazine is decelerated by NTA^{50} , EDTA^{50} , DTPA^{50} , sulphate⁵⁴, acetate⁵⁴ and chloride⁵⁴ ligands. Similar observations were made when NTA and EDTA were added in $\text{Ti}^{III}-\text{H}_2\text{PO}_3$ system⁵¹ and formic, acetic, chloroacetic, methoxyacetic and propanoic acids in $\text{Ti}^{III}-\text{catechol}^{52}$ system. Several other examples are also known. This has been taken as an evidence of operation of inner-sphere mechanism. The complexing ligands block the coordination sites available on Ti^{III} and inhibit the formation of inner-sphere $\text{Ti}^{III}-\text{L}$ intermediate complex or precursor. In the oxidation of hydrazine

by $[\text{Tl}(\text{OAc})]_n^{3-n}$, an interesting LFER³⁷ was noted.

$$\log k_n = A - Bn \quad (22)$$

where n is the number of acetate groups in a complex and A and B are empirical constants. The LFER has the simplest explanation that as the number of acetate groups coordinated to Tl^{III} increases, the rate of the reaction decreases, probably due to the blocking of coordinated sites available to hydrazine. In this connection, it is worth to point out that the rate decelerating influence in some systems and rate accelerating effect of Cl^- in others have been used to classify the reactions of Tl^{III} in two classes (A) and (B). The class (A) reaction, e.g. oxidation of hydrazine³⁴⁻³⁷, As^{III} ³⁸, formic acid⁹ etc., which proceed through intermediate complex formation in the absence of Cl^- ions, occur by same mechanism in presence of Cl^- ions too. The rate deceleration is caused by inhibition of the formation of $\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}-\text{L}$ complex as chloride ion occupies coordination sites available on Tl_a^{3+} . On the other hand, class (B) reactions, which include the oxidation of Fe^{II} ³³, Sb^{III} ³⁴ and $\text{Tl}^{\text{I}}-\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}$ exchange reaction³⁵, are typified by a rate acceleration due to the invocation of a more efficient bridged-activated mechanism with chlorine as the bridge atom.

The hypophosphite and phosphite reactions are unique. In absence of chloride ion, the reactions proceed through the formation of an intermediate complex. Strangely, in presence of chloride ions, the rate of their oxidation is accelerated while deceleration is expected. This finding has led to an interesting proposal of a chloride ion bridged activated mechanism for their oxidation and the formation of following precursor was proposed^{46,47},

Pelizzetti and co-workers^{39,56} similarly indicated the possibility of OH^- ligand acting as a bridge for electron transfer between Tl_a^{3+} and organic substrates like 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl, 1,4-dihydroxy-, 1-hydroxy-4-methoxy- and 1,4-dihydroxy-2-methylbenzenes. In the oxidation of H_3PO_3 and H_3PO_2 , an interesting LFER (23)⁴⁷ was noted.

$$\log k_n(\text{H}_3\text{PO}_2) = \log k_n(\text{H}_3\text{PO}_3) + C \quad (23)$$

A plot of $\log [k_n(\text{H}_3\text{PO}_2)]$ vs $\log [k_n(\text{H}_3\text{PO}_3)]$ was a straight line with a slope of unity; $k_n(\text{H}_3\text{PO}_2)$ and $k_n(\text{H}_3\text{PO}_3)$ refer to respective rate constants for oxidation with $[\text{TlCl}_n]^{3-n}$, where $n = 1, 2, 3$ and 4. The simplest interpretation of the slope of unity is that the relative reactivities of various chloro-thallium(III) complexes in two reactions are the same. This would be true if they react by same mechanism in both cases.

A different line of argument has been used by Mentasti *et al.*⁴¹ to arrive at the same conclusion. They studied the oxidation of a large number of

organic compounds and found that in the oxidation of guaiacol the following reaction scheme operated,

while for the oxidation of catechol and its 3-methyl, 4-methyl and 4-chloro derivatives only the second path was found to operate. They reasoned that an outer-sphere mechanism would not explain as to why in the case of catechol, Tl^{III} did not become a reacting species, as is true for guaiacol, whereas an inner-sphere mechanism could easily explain such mechanistic difference on the basis of different coordination capabilities of the two organic substrate with respect to Tl^{III} . The same workers found that etherification had the effect of decreasing the reaction order with respect to $[\text{H}^+]$ and it was constructed as an evidence for inner-sphere mechanism⁴⁰. Infact the order with respect to hydrogen ions was found to parallel the coordinating capability of the coordinating substrates.

An important question pertaining to the inner-sphere $\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}-\text{L}$ electron transfer reactions arises, whether the reactions are *substitution controlled*, i.e. the formation of precursor is rate limiting and subsequent electron transfer is fast; or the reactions are *redox controlled*, i.e. the formation of precursor is fast but the electron transfer within the precursor to give the successor is rate limiting. As pointed out, the rates of $\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}-\text{L}$ are much slower than the rate of substitution in Tl_a^{3+} and this rules out the possibility of rate of the reaction being substitution-controlled. For this reason, these reactions are considered to be redox-controlled.

It is instructive to compare the kinetic results of the oxidation of hydrazine, amides, phenyl hydrazine and its substituted derivatives (Group I) in which Tl^{III} is believed to attack or bond the nitrogen atom which is also the redox centre (it is undergoing redox change), with the oxidation of arsenic(III), H_3PO_3 , H_3PO_2 , oxalic acid and phenol (Group II) etc. in which the thallium is bonded to oxygen which in turn is bonded to the redox centre. For example, the precursors for hydrazine and H_3PO_3 have been proposed as follows :

The kinetic results given in Tables 2 and 3 indicate that in case of reductants of Group-I the rate of reaction is in general comparatively fast but there is no kinetic evidence for the formation of intermediate complex. In case of the compounds of Group-II in which the oxygen acts as a bridge between Tl^{III} and redox centre, the rate of reaction is comparatively less but there is kinetic evidence for the formation of $\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}-\text{L}$ complex.

The oxidation of two sulphur compounds, thiomalic acid²⁰ and thiocyanate²¹ does not fit in the overall picture. In these cases thallium(III) binds the ligands through sulphur which is a redox centre. But unlike nitrogen compounds, there are evidences for the formation of strong complexes. This behaviour of Tl—S bonded precursors can be rationalised in terms of HSAB principle as both Tl^{III} and sulphur are soft.

Early interest¹ in Tl^{III} oxidations emanated from the possibilities of a single-step two-electron, or two successive one-electron transfers. According to Schaffer's principle²⁷, a redox reaction in which the number of electrons involved in the two half-reactions is equal, the reaction occurs in a single-step, whereas when the number of electrons is unequal the overall reaction involves either a succession of steps or higher order reactions. The latter reactions are in general slow. The literature survey has revealed that when the ligand also undergoes 2-equivalent change, there is no evidence for the formation of Tl^{III}_{s²⁺-60, although the possibility of its formation has been considered by many workers¹. In case of thiomalic acid oxidation, the formation of Tl^{II} has been invoked because the product of the reaction HRSSRH requires the formation of HRS-free radical through one-electron transfer. Secondly, had it been a case of simultaneous 2-electron transfer, the rate of the reaction should have been proportional to [Thiomalic acid]².}

Acknowledgement

The writing of this work is supported by an Indo-US collaboration research project and the work itself was supported by a TRF to one of the authors (D.K.).

References

1. K. S. GUPTA and Y. K. GUPTA, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 256.
2. E. PELIZZETTI and E. MENTASTI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1976, 38, 2005.
3. R. VRATH, B. SETHURAM and T. N. RAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, 21, 414; A. G. FADNIS and S. K. SHRIVASTAVA, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1982, 102, 23.
4. R. J. OUELLETTE in "Oxidation in Organic Chemistry", ed. W. S. TRAHANOVSKY, Academic New York, 1973, Vol. 5B, p. 135.
5. LIMPRICHT, *Ann.*, 1873, 165, 253.
6. Y. ASAHINA, B. SHIBATA, T. KARIYONE, S. KUWADA and M. ASANA, *Acta Phytochim.*, 1924, 2 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1935, 18, 1139).
7. N. A. MILAS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 2005.
8. DUNLOP and PETER, "The Furans", American Chemical Society, Monograph No. 119, Reinhold, New York, 1958.
9. H. N. HALVORSON and J. HALPERN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 5562; J. HALPERN and S. M. TAYLOR, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*, 1960, 29, 174; S. D. SAXENA and K. S. GUPTA, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1977, 108, 813.
10. K. S. GUPTA, S. D. SAXENA and R. SWARUP, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 886.
11. S. D. SAXENA and K. S. GUPTA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, 39, 329.
12. K. S. GUPTA and S. D. SAXENA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, 21, 818.
13. "Encyclopedia of Chemical Technology", eds. R. E. KIRK and D. F. OTTMER, Interscience, New York, 1951, Vol. 6, p. 1007.
14. G. BRIDERMANN, *Arkiv. Kemi.*, 1953, 5, 441.
15. F. A. OOTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1969, p. 154.
16. A. G. LEE, "The Chemistry of Thallium", Elsevier, New York, 1971, p. 296.
17. B. M. THAKURIA and Y. K. GUPTA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, 16, 1401.
18. S. AHRLAND, I. GRENTHE, L. JOHANSSON and B. NOREN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1963, 17, 1567; C. F. WELLS and D. WHATLEY, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1972, 434.
19. C. E. H. BAWN and A. G. WHITE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 339; T. J. KEMP and W. A. WATERS, *Proc. R. Soc., Ser. A*, 1963, 274, 480.
20. C. F. WELLS and M. HUSSAIN, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1971, 380.
21. L. B. MONSTED, O. MONSTED and G. NORD, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1970, 66, 936; V. S. SRINIVASAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 702.
22. K. S. GUPTA, D. KUMAR, S. JAIN and Y. K. GUPTA, unpublished work.
23. G. M. WAIND, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1961, 57, 1370.
24. E. PENNA-FRANCA and R. W. DODSON, *Engenharoa Quimica*, 1954, 6, 1; *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2651.
25. A. C. HARKNESS and J. HALPERN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 3526; C. M. LOVE, L. P. QUINN and C. H. BRUBAKER, JR., *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, 27, 2119, 2139.
26. R. LORTIE and M. ZADOR, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1980, 58, 1305.
27. U. S. BANTHIA, B. C. JOSHI and Y. K. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, 23, 413.
28. K. S. GUPTA and Y. K. GUPTA, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 1180.
29. A. JAHD, J. G. CHAMBERS and M. MCHULEY, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1977, 55, 3575.
30. U. S. BANTHIA, B. C. JOSHI and Y. K. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, 20, 43.
31. P. GUPTA, P. D. SHARMA and Y. K. GUPTA, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1984, 1867.
32. D. KUMAR, Ph. D. Thesis, University of Rajasthan, 1987.
33. P. D. SHARMA and Y. K. GUPTA, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1972, 54; *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1973, 26, 2115.
34. K. S. GUPTA and Y. K. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 11, 1285.
35. V. S. SRINIVASAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Curr. Sci.*, 1970, 39, 254; V. V. YEKSHIN, N. I. PECHUROVA and V. I. SPITSYN, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1976, 21, 972.
36. B. M. THAKURIA and Y. K. GUPTA, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1975, 2541.
37. K. S. GUPTA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, 39, 2093.
38. B. M. THAKURIA and Y. K. GUPTA, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1975, 77.
39. E. PELIZZETTI, E. MENTASTI, C. BALOCCHI and M. E. CARLOTTI, *Chim. Anal.*, 1978, 108, 729.
40. E. MENTASTI, E. PELIZZETTI and E. PRAMAURO, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, 37, 1733.
41. E. MENTASTI, E. PELIZZETTI, E. PRAMAURO and G. GIRAUDI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, 37, 537.
42. E. PELIZZETTI, E. MENTASTI, E. PRAMAURO and G. SAINI, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1974, 1940.
43. A. G. FADNIS and S. K. SHRIVASTAVA, *Osenc. Cult.*, 1981, 33, 1335.
44. R. MENARD and M. ZADOR, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1980, 45, L-217.
45. M. IGNACZAK and G. ANDRIJEWSKI, *Pol. J. Chem.*, 1981, 55, 2613.
46. K. S. GUPTA and Y. K. GUPTA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, 13, 851.
47. K. S. GUPTA and Y. K. GUPTA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, 14, 2000.
48. L. TRIENDL and M. FICO, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1969, 34, 2873.
49. B. FALCINELLA, P. D. FELGATE and G. S. LAURENCE, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1974, 1367; 1975, 1.

50. V. V. VEKSHIN, N. I. PECHUROVA and V. I. SPITSYN, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1977, **22**, 3044.
51. N. I. PECHUROVA, V. V. VEKSHIN, L. A. ZHABORDOVA and V. I. SPITSYN, *Izv. Akad. Nauk. SSSR. Ser. Khim.*, 1977, 1972.
52. E. PELIZZETTI, E. MENTASTI and G. GIRAUDI, *Ann. Chim.*, 1974, **64**, 355.
53. F. R. DUKE and B. BORNONG, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, **60**, 1015.
54. P. D. SHARMA and Y. K. GUPTA, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1973, 789.
55. G. M. WAIND, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*, 1960, **29**, 136.
56. E. PELIZZETTI, E. MENTASTI, M. E. CARLOTTI and G. GIRAUDI, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1975, 794.
57. P. A. SCHAFFER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 2196.
58. N. BHAVANI and K. LILY, *Curr. Sci.*, 1982, **51**, 233.
59. V. S. SRINIVASAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 900.
60. V. S. SRINIVASAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 791.
61. P. D. SHARMA and Y. K. GUPTA, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1975, 81.
62. F. AHMAD and S. KUMAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 567.